

**MISREYA ARKA: PIONEERING PAIN MANAGEMENT IN
UDAVARTINI YONI VYAPAD (SECONDARY DYSMENORRHEA) –
A CASE SERIES**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Secondary Dysmenorrhea, painful menses due to pelvic pathologies like Endometriosis, Adenomyosis, Fibroids, or PCOS, affects 10-25% of reproductive-age women, causing severe cramps, nausea, and incapacity in day-to-day activities. In *Ayurveda*, it correlates to *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad* from *Vata* vitiation, particularly *Apana Vayu*, due to *Vegadharana* and *Srotorodha*, where conventional treatments like NSAIDs offer only palliative relief with side effects.

Method: A case series of five women (aged 26-35 years) diagnosed with Secondary Dysmenorrhea with Clinical examination and Ultrasonography at Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science OPD, Bengaluru, received *Misreya Arka* (24 ml BD) for pain management over two menstrual cycles. Outcomes were assessed using Wong Baker Pain Scale, Verbal Multidimensional Scoring and WALIDD scores pre- and post-

treatment. **Result:** Significant pain reduction was noted (Pain scale from 7-10 to 1-7 across cases), with 40-100% improvement in symptoms like nausea, bloating, constipation, and appetite; co-morbidities resolved in most, enhancing quality of life. **Discussion and Conclusion:** *Misreya Arka's Vatanulomana*, antispasmodic, and anti-prostaglandin effects via anethole effectively managed *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad* by normalizing *Apana Vayu* and clearing *Srotorodha*, outperforming symptomatic medications without adverse effects.

KEYWORDS: *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad*, Secondary dysmenorrhea, *Misreya Arka*, Quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Secondary Dysmenorrhea, characterized by painful menses secondary to identifiable pelvic pathologies such as endometriosis, adenomyosis, fibroids, or PCOS, affects 10-25% of reproductive-age women globally,^[1] with incidence rising post-adolescence due to emerging structural anomalies. Unlike Primary Dysmenorrhea's functional etiology, secondary pain stems from prostaglandin overproduction and *Srotorodha*, inflicting severe lower abdominal pain, back pain, thigh cramps, nausea, fatigue, and incapacitation disrupting work, sleep, and daily functioning in affected cases. Dysmenorrhea, can be correlated to *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad* in *Ayurveda*. Among Twenty *Yoni Vyapad*, *Udavartini* is primarily caused by *Vegadharana*, leading to vitiation of *Vata*, especially *Apana Vayu*, which regulates *Rajah Pravrutti*. Vitiating *Apana Vayu* causes *Rajaso Gamanadurdhwam*, resulting in *Krichrarthava*, *Baddha Raja*, and *Samanthath Varthanam Vayo*.^[2] Conventional therapies (NSAIDs, hormones) provide only palliative relief with adverse effects, creating demand for a safe, effective alternative through *Ayurveda*. *Misreya Arka*, with *Vatanulomana*, antispasmodic, and analgesic properties, offers a holistic solution in pain management.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To understand the clinical aspects of *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad* with special reference to Secondary Dysmenorrhea through a case series.
2. To assess the efficacy of *Misreya Arka* in the management of *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad* with special reference to Secondary Dysmenorrhea.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CASE REPORT

This case series includes 5 patients who attended the Outpatient Department (OPD) of *Prasuti Tantra* and *Stree Roga*, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research Hospital, Bengaluru, and were diagnosed with Secondary Dysmenorrhea clinically and by ultrasonographic evaluation.

A CASE OF IRREGULAR CYCLES WITH ENDOMETRIOTIC CYST

Pradhana Vedana: Patient complaints of pain in lower abdomen, B/L thigh region in the past 4 years.

Vedana Vrittanta: A female aged 31 years with a marital life of 5 years, was apparently healthy 4 yrs back, she developed irregularity in cycle with pain in the lower abdomen region, associated with pain in the bilateral thighs and the lower back region 3-4 days before and during menstruation, along with c/o loose stools, nausea, and headache during menstruation. The pain was severe in nature and hence incapacitated her from doing day-to-day activities. Hence patient approached our hospital in October 2024.

A CASE OF PCOS WITH FIBROID

Pradhana Vedana: Patient complaints of pain during menstruation for the past 9-10 years.

Vedana Vrittanta: A female aged 28 years with a marital life of 11 years was apparently normal. she gradually developed irregular cycle with pain during menstruation for the past 9-10 years. Also, complaints of nausea and headache during menstruation. Hence patient approached our hospital in March 2024.

A CASE OF UTERINE FIBROID:

Pradhana Vedana: Patient complaints of severe pain in the lower abdomen and the lower back region during menstruation in the past 1 year.

Vedana Vrittanta: A female aged 27 years with a marital life of 3 years was apparently normal before one year, she gradually developed severe pain in the lower abdomen and the lower back region during menstruation in the past 1 year. Patient also complaints of pain during defecation, disturbed sleep, indigestion, vomiting, fever and headache during menstruation in the past 1 year. Hence patient approached our hospital in January 2024.

A CASE OF ADENOMYOSIS WITH FIBROID

Pradhana Vedana: Patient complaints of severe pain in the lower abdomen and low back region during menstruation in the past 2 years.

Vedana Vrittanta: A female aged 29 years with a marital life of 2 years was apparently normal before one year, complaining of severe pain in the lower abdomen and low back region during menstruation. The pain is severe in nature, and the patient is dependent on analgesics for most days of her menstruation. Patient also complains of dysuria, constipation and reduced appetite, along with mood disturbances. The patient approached our hospital in July 2024.

A CASE OF PCOS WITH ADENOMYOSIS

Pradhana Vedana: Patient complaints of severe pain in the lower abdomen and low back region during all the days of menstruation in the past 1 year.

Vedana Vrittanta: A female patient aged 26 years with a marital life of 2 years was apparently normal before one year, gradually developed irregular cycle with severe pain in the lower abdomen and low back region during all the days of menstruation in the past 1 year. The pain is so severe that it incapacitates her day-to-day activities. The patient also complains of vomiting, loose stools, loss of appetite and fatigue during menstruation. The patient approached our hospital in May 2024.

Table 1: Personal History.

PARAMETER	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
AGE (YEARS)	31	28	27	29	26
OCCUPATION	Home-maker	IT Professional	Home - maker	IT Professional	IT Professional
MARITAL STATUS	Married- 5 years	Married -11 months	Married -3 years	Married -2 years	Married -2 years
AHARA	Anashana , three meals/day, Vishamashana, frequent intake of refrigerated and stale food	Agnimandhya, Vishamashana, junk food intake.	Regular, feels full after taking a small quantity of food. Habit of skipping meals on and of since 10 years.	Agnimandhya , sudden shift in dietary habits after shifting abroad.	Feeling of fullness on taking a little amount of food, Vishamashana, Katu Lavana Vidahi Ahara Sevana
VIHARA	Acheshta, Diwaswapna	Strength training exercises	Acheshta, Diwaswapna, Fried food items, junk food.	Extensive travel	Acheshta, Alcohol 2times/week, frequent
NIDRA	6-7 hours of night sleep, 2 hours of day sleep	7-8 hours disturbed sleep.	Very disturbed sleep- 2-3 hours of sleep.	Disturbed for 2-3 years	Untimely sleep patterns (post-2 am sleep)
VYASANA	Milk Tea 4-5 times/day	tea ++, coffee ++	NIL	NIL	Alcohol, Smoking
BOWEL	Once in 2/3 days, hard stools	Constipated for 4-5 months	k/c/o constipation since 10 years, currently passes stools on alternate days, hard stools +	Constipated, Symptoms of IBS	Constipated usually, but c/o loose stools during menstruation
MICTURITION	Regular, NAD	Regular, NAD	Regular, NAD	Regular, NAD	Regular, NAD
PSYCHOLOGICAL STATUS	Anxious	Anxious ++, Extreme work stress	Anxious ++	Anxious ++, frequent emotional breakdowns	Normal

Table 2: PERSONAL HISTORY.

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Rajo Vrittanta (Menstrual History)	Irregular	irregular, under OCP for three cycles.	Regular cycles	Regular,	irregular,
Nature of Bleeding,	Normal, clots+ Occasionally.	Excess bleeding, 5-6 pads/day with 100% bleeding till D5 of the cycle.	Normal bleeding	Normal bleeding	Normal bleeding
Interval and Duration,	3days/45-60days,	5days/28-30 days.	4-5days/28-30 days,	4-5days/28-30 days	4-5 days/35-40 days
Pain / Dysmenorrhea	Pain +++low back and B/L thigh region	Pain ++ in the lower abdomen.	Pain +++ from D1 to D3 of cycle- severe in nature over lower abdomen, thighs, low back region.	pain in the lower abdomen region.	Pain ++ in low back and B/L thigh region
Kula Vrittanta (Family History)	Mother HTN +	NAD	Father had DM, Mother has HTN, Thyroid Dysfunction	NAD	Father and mother – DM and HTN
Purva Vedana Vrittanta (Past Medical / Surgical History)	Laparoscopic endometriotic cystectomy in March 2025	NIL	NIL	K/C/O Ovarian simple cysts since 2016.	NIL
Prasava Vrittanta (Obstetric History)	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL
Contraceptive History	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL
Coital History	8-10 times/ month	3-4 times/week no dyspareunia	1-2 times/week, no dyspareunia	1-2 times/week	2-3times/week

Table 3: Athura Pariksha-Ashta Vidha Pariksha.

ASHTA VIDHA PARIKSHA	CASE 1	CASE 2	CASE 3	CASE 4	CASE 5
<i>Nadi:</i>	<i>Vataja Nadi</i> , 76 bpm	<i>Vata Kapha Nadi</i> , 78 bpm	<i>Pittapradhana Vata</i> , 88bpm	<i>Vata Kapha Nadi</i> , 68 bpm	<i>Vata Pitta Nadi</i> , 72 bpm
<i>ala:</i>	once a Day, hard stools.	1-2 Times/ Day, Regular	Once a day, <i>Madhyama Koshtha</i>	once a Day, regular	<i>Prakruta</i> , once a day

<i>Mutra:</i>	6-7 Times/ Day (difficulty in urination)	5-6 Times/ Day	5 to 6 times/day	4-5 Times/ Day	6-7 Times/ Day
<i>Jivha:</i>	<i>Lipta.</i>	<i>Lipta</i>	<i>Lipta</i>	<i>Lipta.</i>	<i>Lipta.</i>
<i>Shabda:</i>	<i>Snigdha</i>	<i>Snigdha</i>	<i>Snigdha</i>	<i>Snigdha</i>	<i>Snigdha</i>
<i>Sparsha:</i>	<i>Anushna Sheeta</i>	<i>Anushna Sheeta</i>	<i>Anushna Sheeta</i>	<i>Anushna Sheeta</i>	<i>Anushna Sheeta</i>
<i>Druk:</i>	<i>Prakrutha</i>	<i>Prakrutha</i>	<i>Prakrutha</i>	<i>Prakrutha</i>	<i>Prakrutha</i>
<i>Akriti:</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Sthula</i>	<i>Sthula</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
MANASIKA STHITHI:	<i>Chinta, Shoka, Baya</i>	<i>Atichintana</i>	<i>Chinta, Shoka, Baya</i>	<i>Chinta, Shoka, Krodha</i>	<i>Chinta, Shoka, Baya</i>
AGNI	<i>Mandagni to Vishamagni</i>	<i>Mandagni</i>	<i>Vishama Agni</i>	<i>Mandagni</i>	<i>Mandagni</i>
KOSHITA	<i>Krurakoshta</i>	<i>Mruthukoshta</i>	<i>Krurakoshta</i>	<i>Madhyamakoshta</i>	<i>Madhyamakoshta</i>

Table 4: Athura Pariksha-Dasha Vidha Pariksha.

DASHAVIDHA PARIKSHA	CASE 1	CASE 2	CASE 3	CASE 4	CASE 5
<i>Prakruti</i>	<i>Vataja</i>	<i>Kapha vata</i>	<i>Kapha vata</i>	<i>Pitta Kapha</i>	<i>Vata pitta</i>
<i>Vikruti</i>	<i>Vata, Pitta</i>	<i>Kapha Pradhana Tridosha</i>	<i>Vata Kapha</i>	<i>Vata Kapha</i>	<i>Vata Kapha</i>
<i>Sara</i>	<i>Twak Sara Purusha</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Samhanana</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Satmya</i>	<i>Vyamishra Rasa Satmya</i>	<i>Vyamishra Rasa Satmya</i>	<i>Vyamishra Rasa Satmya</i>	<i>Vyamishra Rasa Satmya</i>	<i>Vyamishra Rasa Satmya</i>
<i>Satva</i>	<i>Avara</i>	<i>Avara</i>	<i>Pravara</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Pravara</i>
<i>Pramana</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Ahara Shakti: Abhyavarana Shakti Jarana Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama Madhyama</i>
<i>Vyayama Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Avara</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Vaya</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>

Table 5: Examination and Investigations.

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
General Examination	Weight: 55kg Height: 155cm BMI: 22kg/m ² Others: no abnormalities	Weight: 75kg Height: 153cm BMI: 32kg/m ² Others: no abnormalities	Weight: 78kg Height: 164cm BMI: 29kg/m ² Others: no abnormalities	Weight: 60kg Height: 160cm BMI: 23kg/m ² Others: no abnormalities	Weight: 65kg Height: 162cm BMI: 24kg/m ² Others: no abnormalities
Systemic Examination	Mild tenderness + in B/L iliac region	Tenderness ++ Suprapubic region, B/L Iliac Region	Tenderness ++ Suprapubic region, B/L Iliac Region	Pain over left inguinal region +,	NAD
Gynaecologica	P/V – Cervical	P/V – Cervical	NAD	P/S -White	NAD

I Examination	Motion tenderness +	Motion tenderness +		discharge +	
Investigations	USG Pelvis – 18/10/2023, B/L ovaries are bulky in size, with a well-defined, thick-walled cystic lesion, low level of homogeneous shadows measuring: 23 x 18 mm and 22 x 20 mm and 20 x 18 mm on Right Ovary. 32 x 20 mm on Left Ovary Impression – Bilateral Ovarian Complex Cysts – Endometriotic Cyst	USG Pelvis- 20/11/2022, Uterus bulky, Anterior wall fibroid measuring 4.0 x 3.7 cm extending up to endometrial layer, B/L ovary bulky in size, right ovary- 3.3*1.6cm, Left ovary- 3.3*2.2 cms Impression- Anterior wall intramural fibroid, Polycystic ovarian morphology.	USG Pelvis- 10/04/2024, Uterus = AV, Enlarged in size 15.6 *9.1*10 cm, with multiple fibroid Fundus (intramural) = 8.1*8 cm left lateral wall (intramural) = 3.8*3.8 cm and 3.9*3.6cm Rt lateral wall subserous = 5.6*3.2cm and 5.4*3.4cm ET = 19 mm, thickened and hyperechoic Ovary = normal Impression = Enlarged uterus with multiple fibroid and endometrial hyperplasia	Ultrasonography report dated 03/08/2024: Mild adenomyosis and multiple small fibroids noted. 3 adjacent intramural fibroids on the posterior wall measuring 13 X 12mm, 13 X 11mm and 12 X 10 mm 2 anterior fundal intramural fibroids measuring 9 X 6 mm, 5 X 4 mm 2 left posterior intramural fibroids measuring 8 X 7 mm	USG Pelvis- 14/06/2024, Uterus-mild coarse echo pattern seen in anterior wall. Ovaries-enlarged in size shows multiple sub centimetre sized peripherally arranged follicles with increased echogenic pattern right ovary- 2.3*2.6cm, Left ovary- 3.3*2.2 cms Impression- heterogenous echo texture – possibly adenomyosis, Polycystic ovarian morphology.
Wong baker pain scale	7	8	10	9	9
VMSS	8	10	13	10	8
WALIDD SCORE	7	8	10	9	8

Table 6: Nidana Panchaka.

PARAMETER	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
NIDANA	Aharaja Sour curd, pickle, intake of sprouts, potato Viharaja More travelling Hectic work, <i>Atichankramana</i>	Aharaja - Intake of non- vegetarian diet frequently, especially mutton (Minimum 3times/week). Viharaja - <i>Diwa Swapna</i> , Waking Up Late, <i>Avyayama</i>	Aharaja : <i>Abhishyandi</i> , <i>Guru Bhojana</i> , <i>Mamsa Ahara</i> Viharaja : <i>Diwaswapna</i>	Aharaja : <i>Vishamashana</i> , <i>Kapha Vata</i> <i>Vardhaka</i> <i>Ahara</i> (<i>Madhura</i> , <i>Katu</i> , frequent consumption of oily and junk food)	Aharaja – salty and oily, packet food (frequent) Viharaja : Due to Workload and stress in professional life

				Viharaja: Frequent night shifts - <i>Ratrijagarana</i> <i>Manasika</i> <i>Bhava:</i> Stress, <i>Chintana</i>	
POORVARUPA	Pain and discomfort in lower abdomen region 3-4 days before menstruation.	pain in the lower abdomen region, associated with pain in the bilateral thighs and the lower back region 3-4 days before and during menstruation,	Severe pain during menstruation.	pain in the lower abdomen and low back region during menstruation	severe pain in the lower abdomen and low back region during all the days of menstruation in the past 1 year.
RUPA	Severe pain in lower abdomen, low back and B/L thigh region during menstruation.	Irregular menstrual cycle, severe pain during menstrual cycle along with c/o loose stools, nausea, and headache during menstruation	Pain became severe.	severe pain during menstruation also complains of dysuria, constipation and reduced appetite, along with mood disturbances.	The pain got severe that it incapacitates her day-to-day activities. The patient also complains of vomiting, loose stools, loss of appetite and fatigue during menstruation
UPASHAYA	<i>Ushnopachara</i> , Rest	<i>Ushnopachara</i> , Rest	<i>Vatanulomana</i> , <i>Vyayama</i> , <i>Pranayama</i>	<i>Vatanulomana</i> , <i>Ushnopachara</i>	<i>Kapha Vata</i> <i>Hara Ahara</i> , <i>Vikara</i> , <i>Ushnopachara</i>
ANUPASHAYA	<i>Nidana Sevana</i>	<i>Nidana Sevana</i>	<i>Nidana Sevana</i>	<i>Nidana Sevana</i>	<i>Nidana Sevana</i>

SAMPRAPTI OF UDAVARTINI YONI

VYAPAD

Figure 1: Samprapti.

TREATMENT GIVEN

For Pain management as Symptomatic management – *Misreya Arka* 24 ml BD as a pain management from 3 days before cycle until pain subsides for two consecutive cycles.

OBSERVATION

POST TREATMENT OUTCOME

Table 7 Observation.

Case	Wong Baker pain Scale (Pain)		VMSS (Verbal Multidimensional Scoring System)		WALIDD Score		Follow-up / Outcome
	BT	AT	BT	AT	BT	AT	
1	7	4-5	8	6	7	4	<i>Jihwa Aipta</i> , Bowel regularized, severity of pain reduced drastically, appetite improved, Previous complaints of headache, nausea, loose stools during cycles resolved.
2	8	7	10	8	8	6	Appetite improved, <i>Jihwa Aipta</i> , severity of pain reduced, bowel regularized, lightness of body, clarity of mind, symptoms during menstruation reduced by 50-60%.
3	10	8-9	13	6	10	7	Pain during cycles reduced by 50-60%, bloating reduced by 20 % - after 1 st cycle of treatment. Complain of Vomiting resolved, c/o constipation and bloating resolved, Previous c/o tiredness and weakness resolved, Body ache during cycles reduced by 50-60% after complete

							treatment.
4	8	1-2	9	0	9	0	It was a follow up after one month pain not present during cycles , quality of life improved
5	9	5-6	8	6	8	6	Severity of pain reduced by 40%, bloating resolved, and appetite improved, felling of lightness of body. Associated complains of nausea, loose stools reduced by 70 %

DISCUSSION

Pathophysiology In *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad* (Secondary Dysmenorrhea)

In Ayurveda , *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad* mainly arises due to *Nidana Sevana* like *Vegadharana* (suppression of urges), *Abhishyandi/Guru Ahara* (oily/salty junk foods), *Ati Shaya Sukha/Diwa Swapna* (sedentary lifestyle/day sleep), and *Manasika Bhavas* (stress/*Chinta*) as seen in the case series which primary affects *Agni* leading to *Ama* and *Srotodushti* and *Shrotosanga* in *Uttorothara Dhatu Vaigunya* causing *Rajaso Gamanaath Urdhwam* , in chronic condition leads to formation of *Kha Vaigunya* in *Garbhashaya* and *Artava Vaha Srotas* leading to pre disposition of conditions like *Artava Dushti*, *Garbhashaya Granthi*, *Vataja Granthi* and manifests as *Krichartava*, *Baddha Artava*, main symptoms of *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad*.

Discussion On Disease Causing Secondary Dysmenorrhea:

Secondary dysmenorrhea arises from pelvic pathologies that increase endometrial prostaglandin production (e.g., PGF2 α), causing heightened myometrial contractions, ischemia, and pain during menses.^[3]

Discussion On Uterine Fibroid: Uterine fibroids arise from monoclonal smooth muscle cell proliferation driven by somatic mutations (e.g., MED12 in 70% cases), estrogen/progesterone signaling via steroid receptors, and growth factors like TGF- β inducing ECM remodeling and fibrosis. Submucosal/intramural fibroids distort the endometrial cavity and venous plexus, increasing bleeding surface; during menses, they heighten PGF2 α synthesis and mechanical compression of vessels, causing prolonged ischemia and crampy pain.^[4]

Discussion on Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome: PCOS stems from ovarian theca cell hyperplasia yielding androgen excess, amplified by insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia inhibiting sex hormone-binding globulin, alongside disrupted folliculogenesis from elevated LH/FSH ratio and anti-Mullerian hormone. Secondary dysmenorrhea occurs via unopposed

estrogen exposure causing endometrial proliferation/hyperplasia, boosting local prostaglandins and COX-2 expression for hypercontractility; ovarian enlargement adds stretch-mediated nociception.^[5]

Discussion on Adenomyosis: Adenomyosis involves ectopic endometrial glands/stroma penetrating >2.5 mm into myometrium, likely from basal layer disruption, uterine hyperperistalsis, or stem cell migration post-trauma/inflammation. Ectopic tissue induces local estrogen production (via aromatase), upregulates oxytocin receptors and inflammatory cytokines (IL-6/TNF- α), leading to myometrial hypertrophy and fibrosis; menses triggers hemorrhage within thickened junctions, elevating PGF2 α and nerve growth factor for dysmenorrhea.^[6]

Discussion on Endometriosis: Endometriosis originates from retrograde menstruation of viable endometrial cells, coelomic metaplasia, or vascular/lymphatic dissemination, sustained by estrogen dependence (ER- β overexpression), angiogenesis (VEGF), and immune evasion. Implants undergo cyclic bleeding, releasing prostaglandins (COX-2 mediated), cytokines, and neurotrophins that infiltrate pelvic nerves, causing central sensitization and visceral hypersensitivity; adhesions amplify traction pain during uterine contractions.^[7]

Discussion on Endometrial Hyperplasia: Endometrial hyperplasia results from unopposed estrogen stimulation without progesterone opposition, causing glandular proliferation and thickening. Common in anovulatory states (PCOS, obesity), it upregulates COX-2 and PGF2 α synthesis, increasing myometrial hypercontractility and ischemia during menses, thus producing secondary dysmenorrhea. Molecular drivers like PTEN loss (20-85%) activate PI3K/AKT pathways, amplifying proliferation and pain sensitization.^[8]

Pathophysiological Involved

Figure 2: Pathophysiology of Secondary Dysmenorrhea.

General Management

Treatment prioritizes etiology identification via USG, exam, and history, followed by therapy.

Table 8: General Management.^[9]

Line of treatment	Approach	Examples	Indications
First-line Symptomatic	NSAIDs (suppress prostaglandins)	Mefenamic acid, Ibuprofen (start pre-menses)	All cases; 70-80% response
Hormonal	Combined CP/Progestins (thin endometrium, suppress ovulation)	Levonorgestrel-IUS (Mirena for fibroids/adenomyosis)	Endometriosis/PCOS; reduces flow/pain
Second-line	GnRH agonists/antagonists (Elagolix), Aromatase inhibitors	Temporary amenorrhea induction	Refractory endometriosis
Adjunctive Non pharmacological	Heat, TENS, exercise, diet.	Behavioural counselling	Mild-moderate pain
Surgical	Definitive for pathology	Laparoscopy (excision), Hysterectomy (last resort)	Failed medical Rx, severe QoL impact

Mode of Action^[10]**Figure 3: Mode of Action of Misreya Arka.**

Misreya's phytoconstituents- anethole (50-70%), fenchone, estragole-mediate action via

- Uterine Relaxation: Calcium channel antagonism inhibits spasms, countering PGF2 α hypertonicity; *Vatanulomana* normalizes *Apana Vata Gati*.
- Anti-prostaglandin Effects: Suppresses COX-2 and LOX pathways, akin to mefenamic acid but safer; reduces inflammation in *Srotas*.
- Carminative & Digestive: Volatile oils enhance *Agni*, clearing *Ama* (*Jatharagni Deepana*), alleviating bloating/constipation
- Estrogenic Modulation: Phytoestrogens balance *Artava Dushti* in PCOS/fibroids without stimulating growth.

CONCLUSION

Udavartini Yoni Vyapad marked by *Pratiloma Gati* of *Vayu*, *Krichartava*, *Urdhwa Gata* of *Raja* is the *Samprapti* and *Lakshana* mainly involved in secondary dysmenorrhea, manifests across fibroids, endometriosis, PCOS, and adenomyosis where pelvic pathology sustain prostaglandin-mediated hypercontractility, as observed in this series (baseline Pain scale 7-10). *Misreya Arka* demonstrated efficacy by addressing *Vata Prakopa* and *Mandagni* through its *Snigdha-Ushna Guna*, *Deepana-Pachana* effects, and phytoconstituents (anethole-mediated Ca²⁺ blockade, COX-2 suppression), yielding 40-60% VAS/VMSS/WALIDD reductions without GI risks or dependency seen in analgesics. Unlike NSAIDs' isolated prostaglandin inhibition, *Misreya Arka's Vatanulomana* and *Srotoshodhana* resolved co-morbidities (bloating, appetite loss), preventing *Srotodushti* and *Agni Vaishamyatha* in *Udavartini Yoni Vyapad*.

Consent and Ethical Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the International Conference of Harmonization - Good Clinical Practice (ICH GCP) guidelines, and informed consent was obtained from the participant before the study began.

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